

NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE 3D-FLOW CHARACTERISTICS DURING COMPRESSION MOULDING OF SMC

Gustaf Alnersson^{1,2}, T. Staffan Lundström² and Anna-Lena Ljung²

¹ Gestamp Hardtech, Luleå, Sweden; gustaf.alnersson@ltu.se

² Division of Fluid and Experimental Mechanics, Luleå University of Technology, Luleå, Sweden;
staffan.lundstrom@ltu.se, anna-lena.ljung@ltu.se

Keywords: Sheet Moulding Compound, Numerical modelling

ABSTRACT

A numerical model for compression moulding of Sheet Moulding Compound is presented. The model is based on fluid mechanics and the SMC charge is modelled as a fluid with a viscosity that is dependent on the charge temperature, the fibre volume fraction of the material and the shear strain rate. Trends observed in the simulations regarding the shape of the flow front agree with experimental observations in previous studies. The simulations also yield that the type and magnitude of initial heating effects the initial flow to a large extent.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry faces, and will continue to face, significant challenges regarding emissions. In order to overcome these challenges, lighter vehicles are required. Composite materials presents one solution; however, the rapid cycle times often demanded by the automotive industry rule out many common methods. Compression moulding of Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC) is one process that is interesting in this context, given that it has advantages compared to many other methods both with regards to cycle times and costs. For use in the industry it is however required that both the process and the mechanical properties of the final part can be modelled accurately, due to the short development times and high demands on the properties of the part manufactured.

SMC comes in prefabricated sheets of resin and chopped fibres. These sheets are then cut into appropriate size and shape and placed inside the mould. As the mould is closed, the charge is melted and compressed to fill the mould and cure the resin. This is a rather complicated process to model for a number of reasons including: The intricate rheological properties of the charge, three-dimensional effects in the flow front, significant temperature gradients and the presence of chopped fibres that move and orientate as the charge flows. The details of the motions of the flow were studied by, among others, Odenberger et al [1] and Olsson et al [2].

The rheological properties of SMC has also been a topic for research and studied by e.g. Lee 1981 [3], Le Corre et al [4] and Dumont et al [5]. It is found that the main influence on the viscosity of the charge comes from the temperature, the strain rate and the fibre volume fraction. The empirical relations describing these were used by Kluge et al [6] in their work, in which the compression of SMC in a circular section was modelled, with the main focus being to correctly predict the pressure distribution. The flow was modelled fully three-dimensionally instead of being based on, for instance, Hele-Shaw formulations [7-8]. The work presented in this paper aims to expand this model into more complicated geometries, and also to include the air that is displaced during the moulding. This will also allow for more detailed studies of the temperature distribution and the flow field including flow front effects. A better understanding of the three-dimensional flow may lay ground for improved fibre orientation models being a major issue regarding the prediction of compression moulding of SMC.

Existing models for the fibre orientation are usually based on the work of Folgar and Tucker [9] and Advani and Tucker [10], which is in turn based on the concept of Jeffery orbits [11]. The general idea is that the fibres are modelled as single ellipsoidal particles, for which the equations of motion can be

directly solved, with additional term added to account for the fibre-fibre interactions that are bound to occur when the volume fraction of fibres is high ($> 20\%$). It is, however, well established that the model under-predicts the evolution of the fibre orientation [12-13] and several models have been suggested to rectify this, e.g. [13-14] but the results are still not satisfactory for a general case. Another issue that was discussed by Perez et al [15] is that Jeffery orbits are based on that the particles are able to rotate freely, which is not typically the case in SMC moulds. Thus, fibre orientation is not currently included in the model presented here and will be implemented in a later stage.

2 NUMERICAL MODELLING OF SMC

For the numerical simulations, the software ANSYS CFX 17 has been used. Two geometries are chosen for the study, representing two specific cases: the flow around a bend (Fig. 1) and the flow in and around a crossrib (Fig. 2), both of which are features that can be seen in real processing cases. In Fig. 1, the lower edge is an opening, and in Fig. 2, it is the edge furthest to the right. The other sidewalls use symmetry boundary conditions, while the upper and lower parts of the mould are solid walls with fixed temperatures.

The simulated geometries are divided into two parts, where one domain describes the initial placement of the SMC charge, and the other is filled with air and connected to an opening. When the

Figure 1: The bend. Highlighted area indicates where charge is located at start of simulation.

process starts, these domains are compressed in the height direction and the charge thus starts to move. The compression is then continued at a specified speed until the desired final thickness is reached. For all cases presented here, the speed is 2 mm/s.

For the temperature modelling, the initial temperature of the charge is 25 °C for the case with the bend and 80 °C for the crossrib (see Fig. 1 and 2), and the upper and lower parts of the mould have a temperature of 140 °C. The different temperatures of the two charges are used as a means of testing and demonstrating the effects of temperature on the flow. A preheating stage of 6 s is included, in which only the lower wall is heated, to account for the time required from layup until the pressing starts.

2.1 Equations

As was previously mentioned, the charge is modelled as a fluid with a viscosity that is dependent on the temperature, the shear rate and the fibre volume fraction of the SMC. One way to model this is according to:

$$\eta = 3\eta_0 (1 + 100f_f + 1000f_f^2) e^{-B\left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{T}\right)} \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{\dot{\epsilon}_0}\right)^{n-1} (1 + \dot{\gamma}^2)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

, which is taken from Kluge [6]. Here η is the viscosity, f_f is the fibre volume fraction, B is a constant relating to the influence of temperature, T is the temperature, $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear strain rate, n is a power law constant and the subscript 0 denotes initial conditions.

2.2 Discretisation

The mesh consists entirely of hexahedral elements, since it was found that the quality of the mesh was best preserved through the compression. They are specified to have approximately 20 elements in the thickness direction.

3 RESULTS

The flow and temperature in the bend is first evaluated followed by investigations of the flow in the crossrib. Results are thereafter compared and discussed.

In the bend set-up preheating of the compound at the lower wall will induce a temperature gradient before the pressing is started, see Fig. 3 where the temperature distribution in the compound is presented consecutively during the preheating stage. When the pressing starts, see Fig. 3c, the temperature is thus higher in the lower part of the compound.

Figure 2: The crossrib. The transparent section indicates where the charge is initially placed.

(a) 1 s.

(b) 4 s.

(c) 6.1 s.

Figure 3: The temperature evolution during the heating phase. (a-b) before the pressing of the compound while (c) shows the temperature field just after the pressing has started.

Vector plots of the velocity field of the charge can be seen in Fig. 4, showing that initially most of the motion take place close to the lower wall, Figs 4a-d. This can be compared to the experimental al,

results from Odenberger et al, where a similar effect was captured. It is worth noting, however, that in Odenberger this effect was seen more clearly at the upper wall as well. This difference can perhaps be attributed to differences between thermal conductivities and processing conditions. After the relatively dramatic initial flow the SMC moves smoothly over the corner but still an area in the outer corner is not filled, see Figs 4e-f.

To investigate this further the viscosity of the charge is also plotted, seen in Fig. 5a-f. A distinct area of lower viscosity originating from the heating of the compound can be observed at the flow front while the bulk of the charge still has a high viscosity (is not really melted) during the first 0.6 s of the compression.

Figure 4: Vector plots of the evolution of the flow field around the corner. The time between each image is 0.1 s.

Figure 5: The evolution of the modelled viscosity of the charge. The step between each image is 0.1 s. Note the logarithmic scale.

Similar effects as seen for the bend (Fig. 4) can be seen in the crossrib in Fig. 6. The velocity vectors are mainly directed towards the upper wall initially, but the flow aligns towards the outlet later on. However, the layer closest to the wall does not leave as rapidly as in the previous example.

One possible reason for this is that the viscosity in the crossrib does not have as large gradients as for the bend geometry when the compression is initiated, compare Figs. 5 and 7. This is probably an effect of the fact that the compound temperature at the start of the preheating is 80 °C in the crossrib mould, while the initial charge temperature is only 25 °C in the mould with a bend. If Fig. 5 and 7 are compared, it can be seen that in the latter example the viscosity in the middle of the charge is significantly lower than in the example in Fig. 5. This suggests that for the case with the higher temperature charge, the temperature difference between the region near the wall and the middle region is not large enough to behave differently from a more normal squeeze flow.

Figure 6: Vector plots of the velocity in the flow front. The times indicate the time that has passed since pressing started.

Figure 7: The modelled viscosity of the charge during pressing. The times indicate the time that has passed since pressing started. Note the logarithmic scale.

As previously discussed the bend geometry will, together with the compression, produce an observably laminar flow front with velocity vectors in the main flow direction after the bend. Velocity vectors in the flow direction are also seen in the crossrib mould, where the flow has almost obtained a laminar flow profile already before the ribs. Movement over the ribs does not seem to distinctly change the appearance of the flow front initially, as the fronts are similar before and after the rib.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A numerical model of compression moulding of SMC has been presented. The charge has been modelled as a fluid with a viscosity based on the temperature, the shear rate and the fibre volume fraction. Some results from the model have also been presented, and trends observed in the simulation results regarding the shape of the flow front agree with experimental observations in previous studies. The simulations also yield that the type and magnitude of initial heating effects the initial flow to a large extent.

The model is still in development, and there are several features that will be included in future works, such as a better interface between the air and the charge and some implementation for fibre orientation. Also the thermal boundary conditions need to be scrutinized.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is a part of the PROSICOMP project, funded by the Swedish Research Innovation Agency and the industrial partners. It is also sponsored by LIGHTer, a VINNOVA strategic innovation programme.

REFERENCES

- [1] Odenberger, P. T., Andersson, H. M., & Lundström, T. S. (2004). Experimental flow-front visualisation in compression moulding of SMC. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 35(10), 1125–1134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.03.019>
- [2] Olsson, N. E. J., Lundström, T. S., & Olofsson, K. (2009). Design of experiment study of compression moulding of SMC. *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, 38, 426–432.
- [3] Lee, L. J., Marker, L. F., & Griffith, R. M. (1981). The rheology and mold flow of polyester sheet molding compound. *Polymer Composites*, 2(4), 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.750020412>
- [4] Le Corre, S., Orgéas, L., Favier, D., Tourabi, A., Maazouz, A., & Venet, C. (2002). Shear and compression behaviour of sheet moulding compounds. *Composites Science and Technology*, 62(4), 571–577. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(01\)00151-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(01)00151-8)
- [5] Dumont, P., Orgéas, L., Le Corre, S., & Favier, D. (2003). Anisotropic viscous behavior of sheet molding compounds (SMC) during compression molding, 19, 625–646.
- [6] Kluge, N. J., Lundström, T. S., Westerberg, L. g., & Olofsson, K. (2015). Compression moulding of sheet moulding compound: Modelling with computational fluid dynamics and validation. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 34(6), 479–492. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0731684415573981>
- [7] Batchelor, G. K. (1967). *An Introduction to Fluid Mechanics*. Cambridge University Press.
- [8] Lee, C., Folgar, F., & Tucker, C. L. (1984). Simulation of Compression Molding for Fiber-Reinforced Thermosetting Polymers. *Journal of Engineering for Industry*, 106(2), 114. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3185921>
- [9] Folgar, F., & Tucker, C. L. (1984). Orientation Behavior of Fibers in Concentrated Suspensions. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 3(2), 98–119. <https://doi.org/10.1177/073168448400300201>

- [10] Advani, S. G., & Tucker, C. L. (1987). The Use of Tensors to Describe and Predict Fiber Orientation in Short Fiber Composites. *Journal of Rheology*, 31(8), 751–784. <https://doi.org/10.1122/1.549945>
- [11] Jeffery, G. B. (1922). The Motion of Ellipsoidal Particles Immersed in a Viscous Fluid. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, 102, 161–179.
- [12] Sepehr, M., Carreau, P. J., Moan, M., & Ausias, G. (2004). Rheological properties of short fiber model suspensions. *Journal of Rheology*, 48(5), 1023–1048. <https://doi.org/10.1122/1.1773783>
- [13] Wang, J., O’Gara, J. F., & Tucker, C. L. (2008). An objective model for slow orientation kinetics in concentrated fiber suspensions: Theory and rheological evidence. *Journal of Rheology*, 52(5), 1179–1200. <https://doi.org/10.1122/1.2946437>
- [14] Tseng, H.-C., Chang, R.-Y., & Hsu, C.-H. (2016). An objective tensor to predict anisotropic fiber orientation in concentrated suspensions. *Journal of Rheology*, 60, 215–224.
- [15] Perez, M., Scheuer, A., Abisset-Chavanne, E., Chinesta, F., & Keunings, R. (2016). A multi-scale description of orientation in simple shear flows of confined rod suspensions. *Journal of Non-Newtonian Fluid Mechanics*, 233, 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnnfm.2016.01.011>